

Desymmetrizing heteroleptic [Cu(P[^]P)(N[^]N)][PF₆] compounds: effects on structural, dynamic and photophysical properties

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Figure S1. HMBC spectrum of **2** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, acetone- d_6 , 298 K). * = acetone- d_6 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$) or residual acetone- d_5 (in ^1H); ** = H_2O .

Figure S2. HMBC spectrum of **2** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, acetone- d_6 , 298 K). * = acetone- d_6 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$) or residual acetone- d_5 (in ^1H); ** = H_2O .

Figure S3. HMOC spectrum of **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). * = CDCl_3 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$) or residual CHCl_3 (in ^1H); ** = H_2O .

Figure S4. HMBC spectrum of **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K). * = CDCl_3 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$) or residual CHCl_3 (in ^1H); ** = H_2O .

Figure S5. ORTEP representation of the structure of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(\mathbf{3})]^+$ cation in $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(\mathbf{3})][\text{PF}_6] \cdot 0.5\text{Et}_2\text{O}$. Ellipsoids are drawn at a 40% probability level and H atoms are omitted; the phenyl ring in ligand **3** was orientationally disordered and the rings were refined isotropically.

Figure S6. π -Stacking interaction in the $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(\mathbf{3})]^+$ cation and the proximity of proton H^{A6} to these phenyl rings.

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Figure S23. Part of the NOESY spectra (500 MHz, acetone-d₆, 298 K) of (a) [Cu(xantphos)(2)][PF₆] and (b) [Cu(POP)(2)][PF₆]. EXSY peaks appear in the opposite phase (blue) to NOESY crosspeaks (red), and are observed between H^{D2} and H^{D2'} in [Cu(POP)(2)][PF₆] but not in [Cu(xantphos)(2)][PF₆]. * The signal for D2' overlaps with signals assigned to E2, C4 and C6.

Figure S24. Three successive scans in the cyclic voltammograms of [Cu(POP)(2)][PF₆] (left) and [Cu(xantphos)(2)][PF₆] (right). Propylene carbonate solutions, and referenced internally to Fc/Fc⁺ = 0.0 V; [tBu₄N][PF₆] as supporting electrolyte and scan rate of 0.1 V s⁻¹.